

NOTES

(ii) 3-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)-*s*-triazolo(3,4-*b*)benzothiazole :

The 2-*p*-hydroxyphenyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone prepared (by condensing *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole) (1.20 g) was taken in (8 ml) acetic acid. Leadtetraacetate (3.2 g) was added to the acetic acid solution and refluxed for half an hour. The contents were poured over water. The compound separated as per the procedure described in (i).

(iii) 3-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)-*s*-triazolo(3, 4-*b*)benzothiazole :

(1 gm) *o*-Hydroxyphenyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone was taken in (8 ml) acetic acid and (3.2 g) Leadtetraacetate refluxed for 15 minutes. Isolation as described in (i) compound recrystallised from alcohol.

(iv) 3(2'-Pyridyl)-*s*-triazolo(3, 4-*b*)benzothiazole :

(1 gm) hydrazone (3.2 g) Leadtetraacetate and (12 ml) acetic acid refluxed for 20 minutes. Isolation as in (i). Recrystallised from benzene.

(v) 3(2'-Thienyl)-*s*-triazolo(3,4-*b*)benzothiazole :

(1 gm) Thienyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone (3.5 g) Leadtetraacetate and (10 ml) acetic acid refluxed for 30 minutes. The compound recrystallised from benzene.

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Studies Related to 1-Substituted Anilino-Malonyl-3-Methyl-4-(*o*-Nitrophenyl-Azo)-2-Pyrazolin-5-ones*

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PYRAZOLONE derivatives have often shown therapeutic^{1,2,3,4} activities and have been used as dyes⁵. Rathore and Ittyerah⁶ have synthesised acid hydrazides of malon-anilic acid series with the view to assess their antitubercular activity. Though vast amount of work has been done on the synthesis of pyrazolone-azo dyes, no studies have appeared on the formation of dyes using acid hydrazides of malon-anilic acid series.

Our interest was, therefore, focussed on the synthesis of new pyrazolone-azo dyes having structural features of acid hydrazides of malon-anilic acid series and pyrazolone-azo group.

Treatment of *o*-nitrobenzenediazoniumchloride with ethylacetoacetate gave ethyl- α -(*o*-nitrophenyl-azo)acetoacetate which on condensation with malon-anilic acid hydrazides furnished new dyes of the type I. Considerable improvement in the size of the yield of the dyes(I) has been observed when condensations were done in presence of a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid.

Data concerning the dyes are presented in Table 1. These dyes are high melting yellow or orange in colour and are soluble in common organic solvents.

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Dyeing characteristics of three dyes (Sl. No. 1, 2 & 8) have been worked out for wool, silk, cotton and terylene. The dyes imparted bright orange shades on wool and light yellow shades on cotton, silk and terylene. Except on wool the shades were not fast to light and washing.

TABLE I—1-SUBSTITUTED-ANILINO-MALONYL-4-(*o*-NITROPHENYL-AZO)-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONES

Sl. No.	Dye I R	Colour	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Calc.
1.	H	o.r.	235	85.78	20.71	20.58
2.	CH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	l.y.	232	40.28	20.20	19.90
3.	CH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	l.o.	235	42.65	20.00	19.90
4.	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	l.y.	227	45.00	20.00	19.90
5.	Cl(<i>o</i>)	l.o.	235	49.77	18.97	19.00
6.	Cl(<i>m</i>)	o.	236	42.98	18.80	19.00
7.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	y.	221	45.25	19.20	19.00
8.	OC ₂ H ₅ (<i>o</i>)	o.	235	22.12	18.77	18.58
9.	OC ₂ H ₅ (<i>p</i>)	l.o.	230	39.82	18.62	18.58
10.	C ₂ H ₅ (<i>o</i>)	l.b.	230	29.81	19.33	19.26

Colour: o.r.=orange red, l.y.=light yellow,
l.o.=light orange, o=orange, l.b.=light brown, y=yellow.

The products (I) have been screened for their bacteriostatic activity against *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *C. albicans*, *C. neoformis*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis* and *A. migei* at concentration 100 µg/ml. None of the products showed any significant activity.

Infrared spectra⁷: Infrared spectrum of 1-anilino-malonyl-3-methyl-4-(*o*-nitrophenyl-azo)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (I, R=H) has strong band at 1680 cm⁻¹ attributable to the cyclic C=O frequency⁷. The band at 1500 cm⁻¹ shows C-NO₂ stretching, a band at 1610 cm⁻¹ is assignable to pyrazolone C=N (cyclic carbon-nitrogen double bond)⁷. Azo frequency⁷ (-N=N-) has broad peak from 1585-1555 cm⁻¹.

The other peaks appeared due to C-CH₃ stretching at 1340 cm⁻¹, -CH₂- bending vibration at 1445 cm⁻¹ and C-H stretching at 3080 cm⁻¹. *o*-Disubstituted benzene has strong band near 750 cm⁻¹ and -NH- stretching vibration of secondary amide (-CONH) are in the 3100-3300 cm⁻¹ region. For infrared spectra KBr pellet was used.

NMR evidence⁸: The nmr spectrum (TFA) of the dye (I, R=H) contained sharp peak for aryl proton at 7.34 ppm. (δ) and 3-methyl protons absorbed single peak at 2.4 ppm. There is one peak in the 7.85 ppm region corresponding to the proton at C₄. TMs is a standard signal.

Experimental

Ethyl- α -(*o*-nitrophenyl-azo)acetoacetate⁵ and malon-anilic acid hydrazides⁶ were prepared by the methods reported in the literature.

Synthesis of 1-anilino-malonyl-3-methyl-4-(*o*-nitrophenyl-azo)-2-(pyrazolin-5-one(I, R=H))

General Procedure:

Solution of ethyl- α -(*o*-nitrophenyl-azo)acetoacetate (0.280 g; 0.001 mole) and malon-anilic acid hydrazide (0.190 g; 0.001 mole) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid was refluxed for two hours. The contents were concentrated and cooled in ice when the solid separated out. On recrystallisation from aqueous acetic acid the dye was obtained in orange red needles. Yield: 0.350 g (85.78%). M.P. 235°.

Found: N, 20.71; C₁₅H₁₆O₅N₆ requires: N, 20.58%.

Dyeing Procedure: 1% solution of the dye was prepared by dissolving the dye (0.1 g) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (1%, 10 ml). Fibres were boiled with sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml, 1%) for twenty minutes and washed with water. Prewetted fibres were placed in solution of the dye containing 1% solution of mordant and aqueous acetic acid (1.0 ml). Temperature was raised to 90° and the fibres left at this temperature for two hours. The fibres were washed with water, soap and water and dried in air.

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